

Journal of Pure and Applied
Ultrasonics

Website : www.ultrasonicsindia.org

A Publication of Ultrasonics Society of India

Temperature dependent ultrasonic characterization of wurtzite boron nitride

Chandreshvar Prasad Yadav* and Dharmendra Kumar Pandey

Department of Physics, P.P.N. (P.G.) College,
Kanpur-208 001, India

*E-mail: cpy99physics@gmail.com

The present study encloses the evaluation of second order elastic constants of wurtzite boron nitride (w-BN) in temperature range 300K-1800K using the many body interaction potential model approach. Orientation and temperature dependent ultrasonic velocity, thermal relaxation time and other related thermo-physical parameters (Debye average velocity, Debye temperature, specific heat, thermal energy density and thermal conductivity) are also calculated using evaluated second order elastic constants and other known parameters of w-BN. It is found that thermal relaxation time is least for the wave propagation along 55° from the unique axis of crystal at each temperature. The orientation dependent thermal relaxation time of w-BN is predominantly affected by the Debye average velocity while the temperature dependent thermal relaxation time is governed by thermal conductivity. The calculated elastic and ultrasonic properties of w-BN are compared with the properties of other wurtzite structured materials for the complete analysis and characterization of material.

Keywords: Elastic constants, ultrasonic velocities, thermal conductivity, thermal relaxation time.

Introduction

Boron nitride is low porosity white solid material. Boron nitride (BN) can stably exist in many polymorphs because B and N atoms can bind together by sp^2 and sp^3 hybridizations. Boron nitride can be found in hexagonal/layered graphite like phase (h-BN, r-BN), turbostratic (t-BN), cubic diamond-like phase (c-BN), wurtzite-like phase (w-BN), layered graphite-like phase (h-BN or r-BN)^{1,2}. The boron nitride is normally found in the hexagonal phase. Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) is the stable phase under ambient conditions while cubic BN and wurtzite BN were synthesized from h-BN at high temperature and high pressure¹⁻³.

The wurtzite phase of BN phase is metastable phase in nature. The keen interest for the study of this material is due to its technological features like extreme hardness, high melting point, interesting dielectric and thermal behaviour. Structural, mechanical, electronic properties, and stability of boron nitride (BN) in *Pnma* structure were studied using first-principles calculations by Cambridge Serial Total Energy Package (CASTEP) plane-wave code, and the calculations were performed with the local density approximation⁴. Thermal

conductivity of h-BN, c-BN, t-BN, r-BN and its composites are reported elsewhere^{1,2,5,6}. For the thermal management applications, BN is found to be electrically insulating counterpart of graphene^{7,8}. Insulating behaviour of this material along with its high thermal conductivity generates a new concept for the electronic industry.

The structural, elastic, mechanical and acoustical properties of different phases of BN were determined by several researcher using X-ray diffraction, pseudo-potential, DFT methods^{1,2,9-14}. Wurtzite phase of BN belong to III group nitrides as GaN, AlN, InN^{13,14} but very few work have been performed for the elastic, thermal and ultrasonic characterization of w-BN. Therefore the present study is focused on the elastic and ultrasonic characterization of w-BN.

The theoretical evaluation of second order elastic constants of wurtzite boron nitride (w-BN) has been performed in temperature range 300K-1800K using the many body interaction potential model approach. Orientation/temperature dependent ultrasonic velocity, thermal relaxation time and other related thermo-physical parameters (Debye average velocity, Debye temperature,

specific heat, thermal energy density, density and thermal conductivity) are also calculated using evaluated second order elastic constants and density values. The obtained results of w-BN are compared with the properties of other wurtzite structured materials for the complete analysis and characterization.

Theory

Elastic constants

The hexagonal structured crystals are mainly classified to close packed (hcp) and wurtzite (wz) structures. It has long been recognized that the crystals having wurtzite (wz) and sphalerite (zinc blende or ZB) structures are fundamentally similar despite differences between the two structures¹⁵. ZB crystals are fcc with two atoms per primitive cell, where as wz crystals are hexagonal (C_{6v}) with four atoms per cell. The fundamental relation between the two structures is that the local environment of any atom in either ZB or ideal wz ($c/a=1.633$) is exactly the same through the second neighbour¹⁵. The hexagonal structured crystals have maximum packing fraction similar to fcc. The fraction of the total volume occupied by the atoms is 0.74 for both structures¹⁶. The formulation for calculating the second order elastic constants of hexagonal structured crystals are performed using many body interaction up to second nearest neighbour between the atoms. The expressions for the elastic constants are given in our previous paper¹⁷.

The bulk modulus (B) of wurtzite structure material can be determined by following expression using the second order elastic constants.

$$B_0 = \frac{(C_{11} + C_{12})C_{33} - 2C_{13}^2}{C_{11} + C_{12} + 2C_{33} - 4C_{13}} \quad (1)$$

Ultrasonic velocity

There are three types of acoustical wave velocity in hexagonal structured crystals as one longitudinal and two shear wave velocities that are well related to the second order elastic constants. The velocities can be found in literature¹⁸.

The density of wurtzite structured material can be determined by following expression¹⁹.

$$\rho = \frac{2 M n}{3\sqrt{3} a^2 c N_A} \quad (2)$$

Where M , N_A and n are molecular weight, Avogadro

number and number of atoms per unit cell respectively.

Debye average velocity is an important parameter in the low temperature physics because it is related to elastic constants through ultrasonic velocities. The expression for Debye average velocity (V_D) is given in literature¹⁸.

On the knowledge of elastic constants, the theoretical evaluation of ultrasonic velocity can be done. Debye temperature (T_D) is indirectly related to elastic constants through Debye average velocity¹⁸.

The time taken for re-establishment of equilibrium of the thermal phonons is called the thermal relaxation time (τ) and is given by the following equation:

$$\tau = 3k / C_V V_D^2 \quad (3)$$

Here τ is thermal relaxation time. The quantities k and C_V are the thermal conductivity and specific heat per unit volume of the material. The specific heat per unit volume is function of T_D/T and can be determined from literature^{20,21}. The thermal conductivity of wurtzite structured material can be determined by following expression²².

$$k = \frac{AMT_D^3 \delta^3}{\gamma^2 T n^{2/3}} \quad (4)$$

Where, A is a constant; M is the molecular weight; δ^3 is volume per atom; γ is Grüneisen number; T is the temperature. The constant A is depends on the Grüneisen number and is given by following expression.

$$A = \frac{2.43 \times 10^{-8}}{1 - 0.514/\gamma + 0.228/\gamma^2} \quad (5)$$

Results and Discussion

For the evaluation of temperature dependent second order elastic constants of w-BN, the lattice parameters (a and c) are taken from the literature^{1,13}. The value of m and n for wurtzite boron nitride are taken 6 and 7 respectively. Lennard Jones constant b_0 for w-BN is determined under equilibrium condition and is 7.44×10^{-65} erg-cm⁷. The temperature dependent second order elastic constants are calculated using temperature dependent lattice parameters, m , n and b_0 . Temperature dependent bulk modulus are evaluated with help of Eq.(1) and calculated second order elastic constants. The obtained SOECs and bulk modulus are given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Parameters of w-BN at different temperature and at zero pressure.

Temperature→ Parameter ↓	300K	500K	700K	900K	1100K	1300K	1500K	1700K	1800K
a (Å)	2.550	2.551	2.553	2.555	2.558	2.560	2.563	2.566	2.568
c (Å)	4.200	4.203	4.206	4.209	4.214	4.218	4.223	4.228	4.230
ρ (10^3 kg/m ³)	3.512	3.506	3.499	3.490	3.480	3.469	3.456	3.444	3.438
C_{11} (GPa)	816.1	812.9	806.6	800.3	790.9	784.8	775.6	766.6	760.7
C_{12} (GPa)	200.4	199.6	198.1	196.5	194.2	192.7	190.5	188.3	186.8
C_{13} (GPa)	176.8	176.1	174.8	173.4	171.4	170.0	168.1	166.1	164.8
C_{33} (GPa)	863.1	859.7	853.1	846.4	836.5	830.0	820.3	810.8	804.5
C_{44} (GPa)	212.1	211.2	209.6	207.9	205.6	203.9	201.6	199.2	197.7
C_{66} (GPa)	320.0	318.8	316.3	313.8	310.2	307.8	304.2	300.6	298.3
B (GPa)	400.3	398.8	395.6	392.6	387.9	384.9	380.5	376.1	373.1
T_D (K)	1436.5	1434.1	1428.9	1424.0	1416.4	1411.6	1404.2	1396.8	1391.8

The density is function of lattice parameters¹⁹. The obtained density values are presented in Table 1. The ultrasonic velocities are evaluated with help of SOECs and densities for ultrasonic wave propagation at different orientation from the unique axis of w-BN crystal. The Debye average velocity at different temperature and orientation from unique axis are calculated. The ultrasonic velocities V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_D are shown in Figs. 1-4. The Debye temperature of w-BN is calculated at different temperature which is shown in Table 1. The specific heat at constant volume

Fig. 1 Longitudinal wave velocity vs angle from unique axis of w-BN crystals

Fig. 2 Quasi shear wave velocity vs angle from unique axis of w-BN crystal

(C_V) and energy density (E_0) is obtained using Debye temperature and literature²¹. The values of C_V and E_0 are shown Fig. 5. The Gruneisen number for BN is 0.7²² and the δ can be determined with formula given elsewhere¹⁹. The thermal relaxation time and thermal conductivity are determined with the help of Eqs. (3)-(4) using C_V and V_D at different temperature for wave propagation along unique axis of the w-BN crystal. Orientation and temperature dependent k and τ are plotted in Figs. 6-7.

Fig. 3 Shear wave velocity vs angle from unique axis of w-BN crystal

Fig. 4 Debye average velocity vs angle from unique axis of w-BN crystal

A perusal of Table 1 indicates that all calculated second order elastic constants and bulk modulus decrease with the temperature. Since the lattice parameter of w-BN crystal increases with temperature¹³ therefore inter-atomic distance increases and hence the inter-atomic force reduces with the temperature. This causes reduction in stress bearing capacity of material. Therefore decrease in elastic constant values with

Fig. 5 C_V and E_0 vs temperature for w-BN crystal

Fig. 6 Thermal relaxation time (τ) vs angle from unique axis for w-BN crystal

temperature is obtained.

The SOEC C_{11} , C_{33} and bulk modulus B_0 of w-BN has been reported 982GPa, 1077GPa and 400GPa respectively at 300K elsewhere^{1,23}. The present bulk modulus at 300K is exactly same with reported value. The values C_{11} and C_{33} at 300K are also very close to their corresponding reported values and a slight

Fig. 7 Thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time vs temperature for w-BN crystal

difference is due to the reason that the interaction in present model is considered up to second nearest neighbors. Thus present SOECs of w-BN at different temperature under potential model approach is justified. Since our potential model approach for evaluation of second order elastic constants needs only lattice parameter at initial and provides good results and avoids approximations as required in first principle calculations therefore it is better than the other model. The density of hexagonal wurtzite structured material is inversely proportional to a^2c and the lattice parameters of selected material is reported to increase with temperature¹³ hence the calculated density of w-BN at different temperature is found to decrease with temperature (Table 1). The elastic constants of w-BN are found too large in comparison to same group nitrides (AlN, GaN, InN)²⁴. Therefore the mechanical behaviour will be better than the same group nitrides. The mechanical strength, hardness and durability of the material are related to their anisotropic elastic constants, so the SOECs of w-BN are important in the field of material preparing industries.

The present value of density of w-BN at 300K is 3.512 g/cc and the density given in literature¹ is 3.487 g/cc. Therefore our method for calculation of temperature dependent density is justified. On the basis of mode of propagation there are four types of ultrasonic velocities, as longitudinal, shear, surface and lamb wave velocity. Longitudinal and shear wave velocities are

more important for the material characterization because they are well related to elastic constants and density. The elastic constants of material are related with the fundamental solid state phenomenon such as specific heat, Debye temperature and Grüneisen parameters. Elastic constants are related to inter-atomic forces, coordination changes *etc.*, and also with the fracture, porosity, crystal growth and microstructural factors (grain shape, grain boundaries, texture and precipitates *etc.*). Thus, the mechanical behaviour and anisotropic properties of the material under different physical condition (temperature, pressure, concentration, composition, size *etc.*) can be well defined on the knowledge of ultrasonic velocity.

The temperature dependent ultrasonic velocities (V_1 , V_2 , V_3) and Debye average velocity (V_D) of w-BN crystal at different orientation (Figs.1-3) reveal that all the ultrasonic velocities decrease with temperature while their nature with orientation resembles the same characteristics as the same group of nitrides²⁴. The longitudinal ultrasonic velocity (V_1) is minimum along $\theta = 45^\circ$ for w-BN material and quasi shear wave velocity (V_2) is maximum along $\theta = 45^\circ$ while pure shear wave velocity (V_3) increases with the direction of orientation with unique axis. The ultrasonic velocity is directly proportional to square root of elastic constant and inversely proportional to square root of density. Yet, both the second order elastic constants and density of w-BN are found to decrease with temperature but the elastic constants play dominating role towards the reduction in ultrasonic velocity with temperature. As the elastic constants of w-BN are found very high in comparison to elastic constants of the same group of nitrides (AlN, GaN, InN) therefore the ultrasonic velocities of w-BN have largest value among IIIrd group nitrides. The present value of V_1 and V_2 or V_3 for wave propagation along $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction ($\theta = 0^\circ$) at 300K are 15.7 km/s and 7.8 km/s respectively, while the same velocity²³ values for same direction of propagation are reported to be 17.6 km/s and 10.5 km/s. The good resemblance between reported and present value of velocities authenticate our evaluated data of ultrasonic velocities.

For the determination of specific heat of material, the essential parameter is Debye temperature which is directly co-related with Debye average velocity²⁰. The Debye temperature of w-BN is found to decrease with temperature (Table 1), as the Debye temperature is indirectly related to elastic constants through Debye

average velocity. The reported Debye temperature^{1,13} at 300 K in literature is 1400 K while the present value is 1436.5 K. The first principle calculation reports that the Debye temperature of w-BN decreases with temperature²⁵. The similarity between present and reported Debye temperature reveals its justification.

Figure 5 indicates that specific heat and thermal energy density of w-BN increases with temperature. The similar characteristic²⁵ of w-BN has been reported for C_V . The present value of C_V at zero pressure and 300K is 1.39 J/cm³K (11.65 J/mole K), while the reported value of C_V at same condition in literature is 11.124 J/mole K. The atoms of crystal go away due to increase in lattice parameter. Therefore the loss of heat energy by the collision of surrounding atoms decreases. Therefore C_V of w-BN is found to increase with temperature.

It is obvious from Figs. 6-7 that the thermal conductivity and thermal relaxation time of w-BN decreases with temperature. It can also be seen from Fig. 6 that thermal relaxation time of w-BN decreases with orientation up to $\theta = 55^\circ$ and then increases. The thermal relaxation time is well co-related with thermal conductivity, Debye average velocity and specific heat of material [Eq. (3)]. Thermal conduction is a property of material that measures easiness of heat energy transfer through acoustic vibrations. The bond length/lattice parameter of material increases with temperature. This causes reduction in Brillouin zone and hence Debye frequency and Debye temperature reduce. Due to reduction in Debye frequency, the heat transfer through acoustic vibrations reduces. Therefore thermal conductivity of w-BN is found to decay with temperature.

From Fig. 7, it is clear that temperature dependent thermal relaxation time of w-BN is predominantly affected by thermal conductivity and decreases with temperature. When the ultrasonic wave propagates through crystalline media then there is interaction of phonons of ultrasonic wave and crystal lattice vibrations. Due to this, thermal energy distribution of thermal phonons is disturbed. The re-establishment time of thermal phonons is termed as thermal relaxation time. The transfer of momentum among atoms through acoustic vibrations becomes slow as temperature increases due to increase in atomic separation. This results least disturbance in thermal energy distribution of thermal phonons. Therefore the re-establishment time

for thermal phonons reduces with temperature. Phonon-phonon interaction is one of the major cause for the ultrasonic attenuation in pure crystalline medium¹⁸. Therefore it can be predicted that ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction in w-BN will decrease with temperature. τ for w-BN is of pico-second order which is of same order as reported for similar nitride groups in literature²⁴. The thermal relaxation time of w-BN is received 53.5 ps at 300K. The reported values of τ for GaN, AlN and InN are 32.5ps, 16.5ps and 47.2ps respectively. Hence it can be said that ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction in w-BN will exist near to the ultrasonic attenuations of InN.

Conclusion

On the basis of above discussion, we conclude that our potential model approach theory for evaluation of second order elastic constants is justified for w-BN. The parameters density, elastic constant, ultrasonic velocity, Debye temperature, thermal relaxation time and thermal conductivity of w-BN is found to decrease with temperature while specific heat, thermal energy density is received to increase with temperature. The present temperature dependent properties with known properties of w-BN will open a new dimension for further investigation and application of this material.

Acknowledgements

The authors are highly thankful to Prof. R. R. Yadav, Vice Chancellor, VBS University Jaunpur, U. P. India for his valuable discussion during the course of work. The authors also express their thanks to Dr. S.S.S. Kushwaha, Principal, P.P.N. College, Kanpur for providing necessary facilities and Dr. Shripal, Dr. Renuka Arora, Dr. Satish Chandra, Physics Department, P.P.N. College, Kanpur for their support and encouragement.

References

- 1 **Levinshtein M. E., Rumyantsev S. L. and Shur M. S.**, Boron nitride in properties of advanced semiconductor material: GaN, AlN, InN, BN, SiC, SiGe, 10th ed. *Wiley Interscience Publication, John Wiley and Sons Inc. New York*, (2001) 67-89.
- 2 **Berger L. I.**, Semiconductor Material, *CRC Press Inc. New York*, (1997) 112.

- 3 **Meneghetti P., Hans P. J. and Shaffer G. W.**, Enhanced boron nitride composition and polymer-based compositions made therewith, *U.S. Patent* (2008) US7445797.
- 4 **Zhou H. Q., Zhu J. X., Liu Z., Yan Z. and Fan X. J. et al.**, High thermal conductivity of suspended few layer hexagonal boron nitride sheets, *Nano Res.*, **7**(8) (2014) 1232-1240.
- 5 **Zhou W., Qi S., An Q., Zhao H. and Liu N.**, Thermal conductivity of boron nitride reinforced polyethylene composites. *Mater Res Bul.*, **42** (2007) 1863-1873.
- 6 **Sichel E. K., Miller R. E., Abrahams M. S. and Buiochi C. J.**, Heat capacity and thermal conductivity of hexagonal pyrolytic boron nitride, *Phys. Rev. B* **13** (1976) 4607
- 7 **Balandin A. A., Ghosh S., Bao W. Z., Calizo I., Teweldebrhan D., Miao F. and Lau C. N.**, Superior thermal conductivity of single-layer graphene, *Nano Lett.*, **8** (2008) 902-907.
- 8 **Shahil K.M.F. and Balandin A.A.**, Graphene-multilayer graphene nanocomposites as highly efficient thermal interface materials, *Nano Lett.*, **12** (2012) 861-867.
- 9 **Green J. F., Bolland T. K. and Bolland J. W.**, Theoretical elastic behavior for hexagonal boron nitride, *J. Chem. Phys.* **64**(2) (1976) 656-662.
- 10 **Wentzcovitch R. M., Chang K. J. and Cohen M. L.**, Electronic and structural properties of BN and BP, *Phys. Rev., B* **34** (1986) 1071.
- 11 **Grimsditch M. and Zouboulis E.S.**, Elastic constants of boron nitride, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **76** (1994) 832-834.
- 12 **Shimada K., Sota T. and Suzuku K.**, First-principles study on electronic and elastic properties of BN, AlN, and GaN, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **84**(9) (1998) 4951-4958.
- 13 **Solozhenko V. L., Hausermann D., Mezouar M. and Kunz M.**, Equation of state of wurtzitic boron nitride to 66 GPa, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **72**(14) (1998) 1691-1693.
- 14 **Kanoun M. B., Merad A. E., Merad G., Cibert J. and HAourag H.**, Prediction study of elastic properties under pressure effect for zinc blende BN, AlN, GaN and InN, *Solid-State Electronics*, **48**(9) (2004) 1601-1606.
- 15 **Martin R. M.**, Relation between elastic tensors of wurtzite and zinc-blende structure materials, *Phys. Rev. B*, **6**(12) (1972) 4546.
- 16 **Kittel C.**, Introduction to Solid State Physics, *7th edition John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Singapore, New York*, **17** (2003) 25, 51.
- 17 **Yadav A. K., Yadav R. R., Pandey D. K. and Singh D.**, Ultrasonic study of fission products precipitated in the nuclear fuel, *Mat. Lett.*, **62** (2008) 3258-3261.
- 18 **Pandey D. K. and Pandey S.**, Ultrasonic : a technique of material characterization: in Acoustic Waves, *edited by: Don W. Dissanayake, Scio Publisher, Sciyo, Croatia*, (2010) 397-430.
- 19 **Pillai S.O.**, Solid State Physics : Crystal Physics , *7th Ed. New Age International Publisher*, (2005) Chap. 4 , pp. 100- 111.
- 20 **Kittel C.**, Introduction to Solid State Physics, *7th edition John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Singapore, New York*, (2003) 24.
- 21 **Gray D.E.**, *AIP Handbook IIIrd edition. McGraw Hill Co. Inc. New York*, (1956) pp.4-44, 4-57.
- 22 **Morelli D. T. and Slack G. A.**, High lattice thermal conductivity solids in high thermal conductivity of materials, *Ed. Shinde SL, Goela J. XVIII Ed. Springer Publisher*, (2006) chap 2, pp 37-68.
- 23 **Shimada K., Sota T. and Suzuku K.**, First-principles study on electronic and elastic properties of BN, AlN, and GaN, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **84**(9) (1998) 4951-4958.
- 24 **Pandey D. K., Singh D. and Yadav R. R.**, Ultrasonic wave propagation in IIIrd group nitrides, *Appl. Acoust.*, (2007) 766-777.
- 25 **Bai-Ru U., Zhao-Yi Z., Hua-Zhong G. and Xiang-Rong C.**, Structural and thermodynamic properties of wurtzitic boron nitride from first-principle calculations, *Commun. Theor. Phys.*, **48**(2007) 4925-4929.